

Availability of Physical Education, Sports and Health Facilities and Infrastructure in Junior High Schools of Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu

Nadia Yentika¹, Agus Susworo Dwi Marhaendro², Agus Sumhendartin Suryobroto³, Lilik Herawati⁴, Ali Munir⁵

^{1,2,3}Department of Sports Education, Yogyakarta State University, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

⁴Public Elementary School 74 Rejang Lebong, Bengkulu, Indonesia

⁵Department of Sports and Health Science, Yogyakarta State University, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the availability of physical education, sports and health facilities and infrastructure in public junior high schools throughout Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu. This research is a survey research. The population in this study is all public junior high schools in Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu in 2021, totaling 46 schools. The sample technique of this study with Purposive Sampling is 10 schools that can be reached by school distance, schools can be observed during a pandemic and organize PJOK learning. Data collection techniques through observation. This research instrument uses observation sheets. This research analysis technique uses frequency analysis in the form of percentages. The results of the study can be concluded that the available facilities are 31 types and there are 2 types that are not available, namely softball and softball bats. There is no availability of softballs and softball bats in all schools. Of the availability of these facilities, 97.93% are in good condition and 2.07% are in damaged condition. All facilities owned belong to the school. The tools available are 14 types and there are 4 types that are not yet available, namely jumping horses, single bars, parallel bars and multilevel bars. The unavailability of jumping horses, single bars, parallel bars and terraced bars occurred throughout the school. The availability of these tools has a good standard condition of 96.5%, a good condition of modification of 1.2% and a major damaged condition of 2.3%. Of all the tools available are proprietary. The facilities available are 7 types and there are 4 types that are not yet available in schools. The existing facilities are in good condition by 97.93% and 2.07% are in damaged condition. All facilities available are the property of the school.

KEYWORDS: Facilities, Infrastructure, Physical Education, Students.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is a process or activity in providing changes in attitude, character and knowledge to students to change for the better [1]. The education process today in Indonesia has improved and is more programmed [2]. In Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and skills needed by themselves, society, nation, and State [3]. According to [4] states that physical education is a vehicle for educating children. Experts agree that physical education is a tool to nurture young people so that later they are able to make the best decisions about physical activities carried out and live a healthy lifestyle throughout their lives.

Education can be broadly interpreted as the process of learning from the unknowing to the knowing through the guidance of a teacher. For learning from elementary school to high school there is a type of learning that is useful in training the physical to grow healthy, the learning is in the form of physical education [5]. Physical education is a process of interaction between students and the environment, through physical activities that are arranged systematically to lead to a whole Indonesian person, Armed with physical education theory, learning models, and learning charts, physical education teachers determine methods and learning materials to implement and apply learning [6].

In the teaching and learning process of physical education and health, in order to achieve the expected goals, of course, physical education and health teachers are required to be able to form a harmonious atmosphere in carrying out education, responsive to changes due to the impact of advances in science and technology and creatively create something that has relevance to

Availability of Physical Education, Sports and Health Facilities and Infrastructure in Junior High Schools of Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu

educational efforts, including determining learning variations, so that their students will always receive lessons with pleasure [7]. The advantage of physical activity in general is that it improves physical and psychological health for all human beings, both men and women of all ages. Lack of movement (inactivity) is a risk factor for coronary heart disease [8].

Experts agree that physical education is a tool to nurture young people so that later they are able to make the best decisions about physical activities carried out and live a healthy lifestyle throughout their lives. From the various descriptions above, it can be concluded that physical education is an integral part of an educational education that uses direct practice with physical activities as the main medium to improve and develop physical abilities from all aspects, so that the goals of physical education can be achieved as a whole. Activities carried out in physical education learning are carried out using a learning approach in the original sports.

Interestingly, physical education cannot be delivered optimally without the support of good facilities and infrastructure. Sports facilities and infrastructure are very important in the implementation of physical education learning. This is because not all schools have adequate facilities and infrastructure so that they require maximum improvement of facilities [9]. The availability of physical education learning facilities and infrastructure is one of the benchmarks for the quality of education implemented by schools. The better the availability of facilities and infrastructure, the better the physical education learning process provided [10]. Conversely, the less available facilities and infrastructure, the lower the implementation of the physical education learning process. The success of the physical education learning process can at least be influenced by the availability of adequate facilities and infrastructure. In addition, the process of student participation and activeness in participating in physical education learning is also influenced by student motivation.

Physical education in its implementation requires equipment and equipment that supports learning. Facilities and infrastructure are one of the elements supporting the success of physical education, considering that these subjects require many facilities and infrastructure used to support the achievement of effective learning [11]. In physical education learning in schools in order to succeed optimally is determined by several elements, including: teachers, students, physical education facilities and infrastructure, media, goals, methods, environment, and evaluation [12]. In line with this opinion, learning requires support from various aspects, one of which is learning facilities and infrastructure.

The management of facilities and infrastructure is very important because with the management of facilities and infrastructure educational institutions will be maintained and their usefulness is clear. In management, the school must be responsible for facilities and infrastructure, especially the principal who directly handles these facilities and infrastructure [13]. According to [14] states that means are everything that is used as a means in achieving an end or end. This must make the attention of all institutions or educational institutions. The existence of a process of fulfilling educational facilities and infrastructure will help to achieve educational goals.

In the last one year starting in early 2020 until now, the process and activities of education in general in Indonesia have undergone very rapid changes. The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic has affected the pattern of learning carried out by teachers to students. The availability of facilities and infrastructure in schools that are not necessarily the same and meet these standards also affects the learning process of physical education. The existence of this pandemic outbreak forces teachers to twist their minds and learning methods which of course require facilities and infrastructure for teachers to compile learning materials. Learning carried out at home also forces teachers to assist students in fulfilling the facilities and infrastructure needed by using the tools owned by the school.

Physical education is carried out at every level of educational institutions with various types of facilities and infrastructure. [15] stated that there are several needs in physical education learning from elementary school to college, including:

Table 1. Physical Education Learning Facilities and Infrastructure Needs

Types of Sports	Sarana dan Prasarana
Game	Football, volleyball, basketball, handball, sepak takraw, basketball, baseball, rounders, kippers, slagball, softball, badminton, table tennis, court tennis
Athletics	Walk, run, jump, throw
Gymnastics	Basic gymnastics, Agility gymnastics, Rhythm gymnastics, Aerobic gymnastics
Martial arts	martial arts, taekwondo, karate, judo
Swimming pool	freestyle, breaststroke, backstroke, butterfly style
Outdoor Sports	Hiking/ Traveling, Mountainering, Camping, Cross country

Availability of Physical Education, Sports and Health Facilities and Infrastructure in Junior High Schools of Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu

Based on observations at SMP Negeri se Kabupaten Rejang Lebong in Bengkulu, it shows that the school does not yet have a sports field and the availability of sports equipment that does not meet learning standards. This situation will certainly affect the implementation of physical education learning in public junior high schools throughout Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu. The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic has added to the difficulty of the physical education learning process. The existence of online learning with limited facilities and infrastructure owned by schools and students will affect student learning motivation.

II. MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research used in this study is survey research. Descriptive research aims to describe what is currently applicable. It contains an attempt to describe, record, analyze, and interpret conditions that currently occur or exist. Broadly speaking, this research is quantitative descriptive survey research. This study aims to determine the availability of physical education facilities and infrastructure in SMP Negeri se-Rejang Lebong in Bengkulu Province. The availability referred to in this case is seen from several aspects, namely: type, quantity, condition, and ownership status. In the discussion, availability is measured by adding up (1) facilities available in all schools, (2) infrastructure (tools) available in all schools, (3) infrastructure (facilities) available in all schools. Data is presented in the form of aggregate amounts and percentages (%) which include condition (good standard, good modification, or damaged) and ownership status (owned, borrowed, rented). The step in collecting data is to visit each school according to the research implementation plan. In each school, researchers directly record the availability of available physical education facilities and infrastructure. In this data collection, researchers are accompanied by sports teachers to assist in data filling activities so that the results obtained are more valid. The analysis used is descriptive quantitative by classifying the types of data obtained from observation sheets and grouped. Data analysis used using descriptive statistics is statistics that have the task of organizing and analyzing numerical data, in order to provide an orderly, concise, and clear picture, about a symptom, event or condition, so that a certain understanding or meaning can be drawn.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of research on the availability of physical education, sports and health facilities and infrastructure in SMP Negeri se Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu, the following results were obtained.

1. Availability of Physical Education, Sports and Health Facilities in Public Junior High School in Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu

Physical education, sports and health facilities available at SMP Negeri se Kabupaten SMP Negeri se Kabupaten Rejang Lebong in Bengkulu which consists of 33 types of facilities are obtained 31 types of facilities available at SMP Negeri se Kabupaten Rejang Lebong in Bengkulu. While 2 types of facilities that are not alone in the State Junior High School in Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu are in the form of softball balls and softball bats. This situation shows that softball is not yet available at SMP Negeri se Kabupaten Rejang Lebong in Bengkulu. However, there are many other facilities that are not yet available in some schools. Facilities that are not yet available less than 50% of the total schools are handball games, tennis rackets, iron stakes, high jump bars, small flags, maces, gymnastics sticks, gymnastics jumping ropes and chest numbers. Based on the overall obtained existing needs. This situation shows that the existence and availability of physical education, sports and health facilities in SMP Negeri se Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu still need to be improved to support the process of teaching and learning activities.

The availability of facilities and infrastructure that not all schools have, the school has made several modifications. In line with the opinion [11] stated several examples in modifying physical education facilities and infrastructure, including for tools if there is no high jump tub or long jump tub or less number, it can be tricked with a mattress or artificial mattress. In line with this opinion, there is a modification of the long jump tub in the Rejang Lebong Regency Public Junior High School in Bengkulu.

The availability of physical education, sports and health facilities in SMP Negeri se Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu which is owned by 31 types of facilities, there are 1626 facilities. However, the condition of the facility is 100% a facility with standard quality. The condition of the facilities is that there are 1584 tools or 97.93% in good condition and 42 tools or 2.07% in damaged condition. This situation shows that the facilities that have been owned can be almost entirely used or in good condition.

Facilities and infrastructure in physical education learning must be maintained properly and correctly according to the type of material and type of manufacture so that it can be used properly and durably [8]. The condition of this good facility will greatly support the continuity of the teaching and learning process of physical education, sports and health in SMP Negeri se Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu. The support of educational facilities that are almost all available can be said to be very useful for the continuity of learning. Alat-Sports equipment usually cannot last for a long time, the equipment will be damaged if often used in physical education learning activities, so that the equipment can last a long time must be maintained properly [7].

Availability of Physical Education, Sports and Health Facilities and Infrastructure in Junior High Schools of Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu

The learning process of physical education, sports and health is very dependent on the ownership of supporting facilities. The availability of facilities from 31 types of facilities is 100% owned by schools in SMP Negeri se Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu. This situation shows that the ownership of these facilities the school can already fulfill it independently. Although the availability is not yet maximized. There needs to be improvements in order to fulfill physical education, sports and health facilities in public junior high schools in Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu. Facilities are very important considering that physical education, sports and health teaching and learning activities require safe and comfortable facilities so that their fulfillment must be prioritized.

2. Availability of Physical Education, Sports and Health Infrastructure in Public Junior High School in Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu

The availability of infrastructure is divided into two types, namely tools and supporting facilities for learning activities. The existence of tool infrastructure from 18 types of tools that are expected to be available at SMP Negeri in Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu can only provide 14 types of tools. Tools that could not yet be available were saddle horses, single mangers, parallel bars and multilevel bars. This situation shows that this type of tool cannot be available in all public junior high schools in Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu. Of the 14 types of tools available, there are tools that are not widely owned by public junior high schools in Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu, namely high jump poles, jumping chests, jumping horses and balance beams. Overall, physical education, sports and health infrastructure tools in SMP Negeri se Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu are only available by 50%. It can be said that this tool is still not available properly in public junior high schools in Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu. The availability of infrastructure that not all schools have, the school has made several modifications. In line with the opinion [4] states that for facilities if not available it is very difficult to modify. However, if it is available even though it is not qualified, then the teacher can modify it according to the teacher's creativity and student needs. There are also football game learning facilities where two fields that have non-standard sizes are used as football learning facilities. In addition, there is still the use of the school yard as an arena for physical education learning activities. The condition of the availability of physical education, sports and health learning equipment infrastructure at the State Junior High School in Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu is almost entirely in good condition. In detail, there are 96.5% of tools in good condition with standard quality, there are 1.2% of tools in good condition with modified quality, namely in the form of long jump benchmark beams and there are 2.3% of damaged tools. The availability of this new 50% tool is almost entirely usable. All available tools are all owned by public junior high schools in Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu. This situation shows that the ownership status of the tools is entirely owned by schools in SMP Negeri se Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu.

The state of the facilities in SMP Negeri se Kabupaten Rejang Lebong in Bengkulu explained that of the 11 facilities expected to exist, schools in SMP Negeri se Kabupaten Rejang Lebong in Bengkulu only have 7 types of facilities. However, this situation is only 34.5% of schools that have among the 7 types of facilities. Facilities owned by all schools are basketball courts, volleyball courts and school yards or sports venues. While the minimal facilities owned by schools in SMP Negeri se Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu are football fields there are 2 schools, badminton courts there are 2 schools, gymnastics halls there are 2 schools, jumping tubs there are 2 schools. Facilities that are not yet owned by all schools are softball fields, running tracks, tennis courts and swimming pools. The results of the study showed that ownership of facilities was still minimal and lacking in public junior high schools in Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu. This situation shows that the existence of facilities still needs to be developed behind the limitations of schools.

From the ownership of the above facilities, it can be detailed that there are 83.1% standard facilities in good condition, 15.5% large modification facilities in good condition and 1.4% damaged facilities in the form of volleyball courts. The facilities that are owned almost entirely in good condition show that the facilities can be used optimally to reduce the limitations of existing facilities in public junior high schools in Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu.

IV. SIMPULAN

Based on the results of research and discussion, it can be concluded that the availability of physical education, sports and health facilities and infrastructure in State Junior High School in Rejang Lebong Regency in Bengkulu, which consists of 10 schools, is 31 types available, and there are 2 types that are not available, namely softball and softball bats. There is no availability of softballs and softball bats in all schools. Of the availability of these facilities, 97.93% are in good condition and 2.07% are in damaged condition. All facilities owned belong to the school. The tools available are 14 types and there are 4 types that are not yet available, namely jumping horses, single bars, parallel bars and multilevel bars. The unavailability of jumping horses, single bars, parallel bars and terraced bars occurred throughout the school. The availability of these tools has a good standard condition of 96.5%, a good condition of modification of 1.2% and a major damaged condition of 2.3%. All available tools belong to the school. The

Availability of Physical Education, Sports and Health Facilities and Infrastructure in Junior High Schools of Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu

facilities available are 7 types and there are 4 types that are not yet available in schools. Facilities that are not yet available are tennis courts, softball fields, running tracks and swimming pools. The existing facilities are in good condition by 97.93% and 2.07% are in damaged condition. All facilities available are the property of the school.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author would like to express his deepest gratitude to all students who have been willing to complete this research. It's a journey of growth, discovery, and collaboration, and it wouldn't have been possible without the support, guidance, and contributions of many individuals and entities. As a big expression of gratitude, I express my appreciation to those who have played an important role in making this effort a reality.

REFERENCES

- 1) A. P. Ricky Kurniawan, S. Junaidi, H. Setya Subiyono, and S. H. S, "Survey of Physical Education, Sports and Health Learning Facilities and Infrastructure in State Junior High Schools in Purbalingga City in 2012," *J. Phys. Educ. Sport*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 58–62, 2020, [Online]. Available: <http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/peshr>
- 2) R. P. E. S. Prasetya, "Survey of Sports and Health Physical Education Facilities and Infrastructure in Senior High Schools in Trenggalek Regency," *J. Pendidik. Olahraga dan Kesehatan*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 157–160, 2019, [Online]. Available: http://jurnalmahasiswa.unesa.ac.id/index.php/jurnal*pendidikan*jasmani/issue/archive
- 3) A. Candra, "Review of the availability of physical education and health learning facilities and infrastructure in Smp Negeri Se-Kecamatan Perhentian Raja Kampar Regency," *Prim. J. Pendidik. Guru Sekol. Dasar*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. 373, 2017, doi: 10.33578/jpkip.v6i1.4115.
- 4) Hendriadi, "Availability of Sarpras JPOK," *Univ. Pendidik. Ganesha*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 68–74, 2021.
- 5) K. S. Jaya, I. N. Kanca, and I. K. Semarayasa, "Survey of the Availability of Facilities and Infrastructure to Support Physical Education, Sports and Health (PJOK) Learning," *Indones. J. Sport Tour.*, vol. 3, no. 2, p. 57, 2021, doi: 10.23887/ijst.v3i2.34862.
- 6) V. V. I. Saputri, "Football Sports Facilities and Infrastructure to Support the Extraordinary Learning Process of Temanggung Regency in 2013," *Act. - J. Phys. Educ. Sport. Heal. Recreat.*, vol. 3, no. 11, pp. 1402–1407, 2014.
- 7) M. Ghiffary, "Survey of the Availability of Facilities and Infrastructure to Support Physical Education, Sports and Health (PJOK) Learning at the Junior High School Level in Buleleng District," *J. Ilmu Keolahragaan Undiksha*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 34–41, 2020, doi: 10.23887/jiku.v8i1.29638.
- 8) N. Yuliana and A. W. Kurniawan, "Survey of PJOK Facilities and Infrastructure of State Junior High School in Kademangan District, Blitar Regency in 2021," *Pros. Semin. Nas. Pendidik. Jasmani, Kesehatan dan Rekreasi*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 127–132, 2021.
- 9) F. A. Saputra and B. Djawa, "Survey of the availability of physical education, sports and health learning facilities and infrastructure in junior high schools in Kebomas District, Gresik Regency," *J. Pendidik. Olahraga dan Kesehatan*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 266–270, 2018.
- 10) N. A. Sudibyo and R. A. Nugroho, "Survey of Physical Education, Sports and Health Learning Facilities and Infrastructure in Junior High Schools in Pringsewu Regency in 2019," *J. Phys. Educ.*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 18–24, 2020, doi: 10.33365/joupe.v1i1.182.
- 11) A. C. Pratama and B. F. Kuntjoro, "Survey of Physical Education, Sports and Health Infrastructure, Junior High Schools and Equivalent," *J. Pendidik. Olahraga dan Kesehatan*, no. 19, pp. 561–564, 2011.
- 12) F. Wijaya and A. Rachman, "Availability of Physical Education, Sports and Health Learning Facilities and Infrastructure at Sumenep Regency State High School," *J. Pendidik. Olahraga dan Kesehatan. Vol.*, vol. 05, no. 2, pp. 232–235, 2017, [Online]. Available: <https://jurnalmahasiswa.unesa.ac.id/index.php/9/article/view/21247/19482>
- 13) M. Ngula, Y. B. O. Tapo, and Y. M. Wea, "Development of volleyball passing learning tools with plastic ball modifications as a means of student learning in physical education, sports and health learning at the junior high school level," *J. Edukasi Citra Olahraga*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 126–135, 2021, doi: 10.38048/jor.v1i2.394.
- 14) A. Dhika, "Survey of Volleyball Facilities and Infrastructure in Tegal Regency," *Journal.Unnes*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 188–196, 2020.
- 15) S. Afor, F. Arkiang, M. I. Ola, and S. I. Yanti, "The Effectiveness of Human Resource Management in Improving the Quality of Education," *Urwatul Wutsqo J. Stud. Kependidikan dan Keislam.*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 164–175, 2022, doi: 10.54437/urwatulwutsqo.v11i2.589.